

Evaluating the impact of Living Labs using an AI-augmented framework for enhanced value assessment

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Abstract

Living Labs are increasingly recognized as complex ecosystems where value is co-created across diverse stakeholder constellations. Yet, prevailing assessment frameworks often struggle to capture this multidimensionality without resorting to reductionist or interpretative shortcuts. This paper introduces a hybrid methodology that integrates deductive value mapping with the affordances of large language models (LLMs), aiming to reallocate analytical resources toward deeper engagement with raw data. The approach combines structured frameworks with LLM-supported workshops, enabling iterative reflection and dialogical sense-making. Rather than automating interpretation, LLMs are positioned as epistemic partners that scaffold critical inquiry. The methodology was validated in a Living Lab context, revealing both its potential to enhance analytical granularity and its limitations in terms of interpretive ambiguity. Hence, this approach offers a reflexive and operationally grounded approach to understanding value creation in Living Labs. It invites further discussion on how emerging tools can be responsibly embedded in participatory research without compromising epistemological integrity.

Key words

Living Labs, Impact Assessment, Value Creation, Methodology, Large Language Models

Problem statement

The multidimensional nature of Living Labs makes it challenging to define a unified and grounded way of revealing the different layers of value creation (Santonen et al., 2024; Robaeyst et al., 2024). The wide variety of stakeholders and the diverse range of activities occurring in Living Labs typically cause divergent narratives as to their nature and role (Hossain, 2019). However, in recent years, several researchers have been pushing forward a more rigid and systematic approach to understanding how value is being created in Living Lab environments (e.g., Ballon et al., 2018; Paskaleva & Cooper, 2021; Schuurman et al., 2015). This led to the development of several frameworks and ‘lenses’ (e.g., Ståhlbröst, 2012; Robaeyst & Baccarne, 2024). However, this holds the risk of being (1) reductionistic (e.g., due to limited resources allocated for the assessment), and (2) prone to researcher bias due to highly interpretative epistemological choices (Bronson et al., 2021).

Methods

This study explores emerging methodological paradigms that explore the potential of Large Language Models (LLMs) to bridge deductive (framework-driven) and inductive (interpretative) analysis methods. More specifically, we developed and validated (on a single Living Lab case) a value assessment methodology that combines (1) multiple LLMs in a staged methodology with (2) a workshop-based approach in which LLM-supported interactions facilitate reflection and discussion.

This methodological framework (figure 1) first transforms raw audio interview data into human- and machine-readable formats: a process of transcription (OpenAI’s Whisper³ and High-Performance Computing (HPC)), diarization (pyAnnote⁴), contextualized sentence reconstruction, and systematization (OpenAI API⁵). Secondly, pre-prompted Copilot⁶ strategies synthesize insights on an individual level, maintaining references to original timestamps for validation and facilitating human-computer coding strategies. Finally, a value creation assessment workshop starts from this synthesis (hypothesis) framework, focussing on human discussion and reflection. During this workshop, we explored the role of an AI agent (OpenAI) as a medium to interface between synthesis,

³ <https://openai.com/index/whisper/>

⁴ <https://github.com/pyannote/pyannote-audio>

⁵ <https://platform.openai.com/>

⁶ <https://copilot.microsoft.com/>

interpretations and the raw empirical data. Finally, we compared this approach to a traditional key informant approach (conducted on the same Living Lab case).

Figure 1. Methodological framework for AI-Augmented Value Assessments

Results

The results show that, although caution (e.g., crosschecks and iterative prompt development) and a critical mindset are crucial in emerging research approaches like these, this allows for effective resource reallocation (heavily reducing the cost of analysis). Furthermore, it opens up a discussion on the balance between potentially (too) reductionistic approaches of framework-driven value creation assessments on the one hand, and the need for systemic (deductive) approaches (as discussed above). A non-linear oscillation process allows one to go back and forth between empirical data and interpretation, across multiple analytical dimensions and inter-actor comparisons (e.g., “Is this [insight x] valid for both academia and policymakers?”, e.g. allowing more granular quadruple helix assessments). Beyond **the traditional value assessment report**, an agent embodying the empirical data creates a boundary object that allows multiple readings. However, ethical considerations should safeguard misuse and unauthorized or unintended access (e.g. different levels of pseudonymisation & versatile technology selection). In this explorative research, we’ve applied the framework on a clean ‘single actor’-oriented research context (in-depth interviews), but it would be interesting to study how this approach can be scaled to (messy) multi-method data sets that include focus groups, field observations etc. We’d like to open the discussion on the implications of such approaches in relation to ambiguity versus rigidity, and their implications for the nature of human-computer interpretative approaches to knowledge development.

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